

DE OORZAAK

Large scale façade level participatory monitoring in Flanders (De Oorzaak)

Prof. Cedric Vuye (University of Antwerp)

29/04/2025

43dB
Roodborstje

**HET GROOTSTE
BURGERONDERZOEK
NAAR GELUID**

74dB
Rijdende tram

DeMorgen.

UZA'

 **Universiteit
Antwerpen**

Content

The project in a nutshell

Motivation

Honking the biggest noise worry in city

Cops Seek More Power For Stricter Crackdown

Dwaipayan Ghosh
@timesgroup.com

Kolkata: Honking, according to experts, is the single biggest contributor to noise pollution in Kolkata. The city, along with Assansol, now stands sixth — and second in India after Moradabad — among the noisiest south Asian cities, says the United Nations Environmental Programme (UNEP)'s report 'Frontiers 2022: Noise, Blazes and Mis-matches'.

According to the report, Kolkata's average is 65-69 decibel, way above the maximum threshold of 75 decibels in the day (for commercial areas) and 40 decibels at night (residential areas).

Times View

This needs our immediate attention. Unwanted and unnecessary noise, besides being a major irritant, has mental and physical health repercussions. We should update policies, if needed, and implement the existing rules much more forcefully.

"All forms of musical horns, TT horns and airhorns are banned. Yet, several motorists continue using them. Similarly, there are mandates under the law that silent generator sets are to be used. But for all this, mass awareness is the need of the hour," said a senior scientist working for a Bengal government body. The scientist added: "It is important that taking action — say against airhorns — should not

SILENT KILLER

Where Kolkata stands | Kolkatans are exposed to noise levels ranging between 65 decibels and 89 decibels

Three major contributors
▶ Honking
▶ Loudspeakers
▶ Generator sets

Moradabad 2nd in world in noise pollution: UN report

NOISY CITIES
1. Moradabad (89 decibels)
2. Kolkata (65-69 decibels)
3. Assansol (65-69 decibels)
4. Assansol (65-69 decibels)
5. Assansol (65-69 decibels)
6. Kolkata (65-69 decibels)
7. Assansol (65-69 decibels)
8. Assansol (65-69 decibels)
9. Assansol (65-69 decibels)
10. Assansol (65-69 decibels)

TOI | MAR 27, 2022

What about other big cities
New York | Nine of 10 mass transit users are exposed to noise levels exceeding the recommended limit of 70 dB

Barcelona | Over 72% of the city's residents are exposed to noise levels of over 55 dB

Hong Kong | Two among five are exposed to road traffic noise above the permissible limit

Source: UNEP report

lie with transport inspectors alone." Environmentalists also blame the inaction by authorities to repeated complaints of noise pollution. Green crusader Subhas Datta said: "Kolkata is the noisiest city of India. I personally measured noise level in hospitals way back in the 80s and found gross violations. The same tradition is continuing. Noise is a silent killer as it affects the nervous system. It must be stopped and strict monitoring of ambient noise level must be enforced."

Kolkata Police officers said they will seek more powers under Section 15 of the Environment Protection Act to prosecute people for noise pollution. This penal measure allows for fines up to Rs 1 lakh. As per states, only the Pollution Control

Board can prosecute under this section. At present, police act under the Motor Vehicles Act that allows them to lap-penalise of Rs 500-Rs 1,000.

Kolkata Traffic Police, which launched anti-honking drives last year, has challenged 1,294 motorists in the last 12 days, an average of 222 each day. The Sealdah traffic guard, which covers hospitals like NRS and the BR Singh Hospital, a portion of Medical College and the R Ahmed Dental College, has reported the highest number of violations.

"Scientific and proper diversion of traffic should be implemented to control noise pollution. Involvement of NGOs could help us reduce noise pollution," said expert Dr Roy Chowdhury in one of his research articles.

EYE ON SOUND

Noise pollution levels to be monitored

Chetan Chhabra

ALL ON RECORD

Central Pollution Control Board putting up online stations to monitor noise levels from the clock from November. A first set of monitoring centres will be set up in Delhi, Kolkata, Chennai, Bangalore, Hyderabad and Lucknow. The gathered data will be available at the pollution watchdog's website.

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The Times of India - Mumbai, 12/30/2019

Noise levels during festivals now at their lowest

Source: UNEP report

NOISE COMPARISON

INDIA	135 dB
USA	127 dB
EUROPEAN UNION	123 dB
HEALTH OF INDIA	113 dB
WORLD HEALTH ORGANIZATION	100 dB
WORLD HEALTH ORGANIZATION	100 dB

2019

World Health Organization

NOISE POLLUTION:

Loudness Not Ok Please

Cacophony in cities takes a toll on peaceful living

By [Author Name]

There are many regular data we can suggest the authorities the corrective steps they should take." Gaurav said.

From November, the first set of monitoring centres will be set up in Delhi, Kolkata, Chennai, Bangalore, Hyderabad and Lucknow. Each city will have five monitoring stations covering industrial, residential and commercial areas. The data will then be fed into a central server at CPCB headquarters, which will be displayed on the website.

In the next two years, 25 more cities would be added to the network and all urban areas will covered in five years time.

78 WEST TO

26 ONLY

Summerville

THE LOWCOUNTRY'S NEWS LEADER

HOMEOWNERS FIGHTING FOR PEACE AND QUIET CLAIM NOISE FROM I-26 IS KEEPING THEM FROM ENJOYING THEIR HOMES

Live 5

WCCO

Talked in auto-pedestrian crash in Andrews

World Health Organization

ENVIRONMENTAL NOISE GUIDELINES for the European Region

Partners of De Oorzaak

DEPARTEMENT
OMGEVING

Vlaanderen
is zorgzaam en
gezond samenleven

AGENTSCHAP
WEGEN & VERKEER

lantis bouwen
aan
verbinding

gent:

leuven

Provincie
Antwerpen

5

Universiteit
Antwerpen
UZA

DeMorgen.

natus.

Sorama

> 10 000 citizen scientists

Total budget > 1 million euro + media budget De Morgen > 1.5 million euro

Main project goals

Develop and refine an automatic and "on the edge" sound recognition system using smart sound sensors and artificial intelligence (AI).

Implement an extensive smart sound sensor network in the metropolitan area around Antwerp, Ghent and Leuven for one year.

Develop objective noise maps and associated subjective "perception maps".

Gather detailed medical insight into the impact of noise on the population's health, stress, sleep and quality of life.

Stimulate citizens for science, and inform and sensitize them in a neutral, balanced and scientifically based way about the noise landscape in Flanders and impact of noise on health/sleep/quality of life.

Support and encourage the (local) government to give sufficient attention to this important (and often overlooked) theme.

Supplementary partner goals

Extra research goals:

- Evaluation of the influence of environmental noise on the health sleep quality of the patients at the UZA campus (UZA)
- Follow-up of the construction of a noise barrier (Department of Mobility and Public Works)
- Collaboration with ongoing/future (CS) projects (Department of Environment)

Communication goals:

- Participation in large media campaigns by De Morgen (all)
- Strengthen brand name, extra traffic to website, additional followers in social media channels / newsletters (UAntwerpen, UZA and De Morgen)
- Attract more students and create more interest in science/STEM (UAntwerpen)
- Sell more newspaper subscriptions (De Morgen)

Citizen Science?

Definition: Citizen science is scientific research performed by non-professional scientists (citizen scientists). Citizen scientists can work independently, but they often work together with professional scientists. Citizen science is a very valuable scientific research method. Not only does it generate new scientific knowledge, but it can also generate spectacular results in community building and science education.

Why?

Large amount of data; trade-off between quality and quantity of the data

Why do people take part in citizen science?

Initial participation	Personal interest in the topic
	Contributing to science
	The fun factor, taking pleasure
Continued participation	Desire to learn and general inquisitiveness
	Validation and appreciation for the contribution
	Deeper understanding of the topic
	Contact with the scientist and/or other like-minded people in the project
	Willingness to assume tasks or roles in the project

Source: Rotman et al. [31].

Main research methodology

Smart sensor network

400 citizen sensors
30 reference sensors

1475 citizen locations (2 months)
73 fixed locations (1 year)
3 cities: Antwerp, Ghent & Leuven

Measurements 24/7:

- Noise source recognition
- Acoustical descriptors
- Personal dashboard

Environmental noise:

- Air, rail and road traffic
- Events (sport / music / ...)
- Industry
- Quiet urban areas

qualtrics^{XM} Surveys

Large Sound Survey
Open to Flemish residents
(9939 respondents)

Weekly surveys
1475 participants

Specific surveys
100 participants

Out-of-scope:

- HVAC and cooling units
- Wind turbines
- Gun ranges
- Race tracks

Medical research

Sleep study
100 participants from Antwerp
50 with/without hyperacusis
One night sleep study at home

Stress analysis
Saliva samples

Hearing study @UZA
Hearing thresholds
Uncomfortable Loudness
Levels

Smaller research initiatives

Apple Watch study: use of iPhone and Apple Watch for low-cost sleep study (n = 121)

Soundwalk survey: without (n = 4665) and with dedicated app (n = 1560 & new call-to-action)

De Oorzaak

Six-month follow-up of new noise barriers in Aalter (20 CS + surveys before/after → n = 60/30)

Acoustical measurements at UZA hospital campus and patient sleep quality survey (n = 144)

Participation of STEM teachers and students from 12 secondary schools: sensor + dashboard, teaching package (**HoorLINK**), and surveys on noise exposure and hearing protection

Timeline

Results?

Follow De Oorzaak through these channels (*everything in Dutch*):

<https://www.deoorzaak.be/> & <https://www.demorgen.be/oorzaak> & <https://www.uza.be/de-oorzaak>

Monthly newsletter: register [here](#).

Social media

Live maps at De Morgen

Live measurements [citizen sensors](#)

Measurements with [De Oorzaak app](#)

Participate via the app: [Android](#) and [Apple](#) (first calibrate, then “geluidswandeling” = sound walk)

UZV De Oorzaak

DE OORZAAK

Maak met het analyseren van het geluid in uw omgeving.

Deelbetreft:

Spektrum

Spektrum

Geluidswandeling

Over De Oorzaak

Resultaten

Results?

Scientific results:

- 1) Discussion in the scientific working group → transfer to communication working group
- 2) Newspaper article in De Morgen + possible broader media-attention (press release → TV/radio)
- 3) Presentations at conferences (acoustical/medical/communication conferences)

"DE OORZAAK" - A CITIZEN SCIENCE APPROACH TO ASSESS THE IMPACT OF ENVIRONMENTAL NOISE IN AN URBAN ENVIRONMENT

REGION-WIDE SOUNDSCAPE MAPPING WITHIN A CITIZEN SCIENCE FRAMEWORK (DE OORZAAK): INSIGHTS FROM SUBJECTIVE DATA

CONTEXTUALIZING NOISE ANNOYANCE: LESSONS FROM THE "LARGE SOUND SURVEY" WITHIN THE CITIZEN-SCIENCE PROJECT "DE OORZAAK"

75th ANNUAL ICA CONFERENCE
12-16 JUNE 2025 | DENVER, COLORADO, USA

Factors influencing noise annoyance across various transportation modes: lessons from the citizen science project "De Oorzaak"

FORUM ACUSTICUM
EURONOISE 2025

7th ABAV Research Day

Thursday, November 21, 2024
9:30 AM - 6:00 PM

- 4) Final symposia and reports (in Dutch - end of September 2025)
- 5) Journal publications (upcoming)

Teaser 1: soundwalk survey

Anonymous soundwalk survey - response

- 4665 completed answers
(20/10/2023 - 05/03/2024)
- 2/3 from urban areas, 1/3 rural areas
- Antwerp + Ghent + Leuven = 35% of the answers
- Daytime: 80.5%, Evening: 11.8% Nighttime: 7.6%
- 55.1% women and 43.6% men
- Mean age = 51.9 years (SD=13.8)

https://ablenya.github.io/Oorzaak/Soundscape_maps_English.html

Anonymous soundwalk survey – first conclusions

- Combination of soundscape survey data with GIS data (e.g. Flemish Green Maps, Quiet Areas in Flanders, EU Quietness Suitability Index, ...)
- First conclusions:
 - Effectively hearing natural sounds strongly predicts positive soundscape experiences → journal paper by Van Renterghem et al. → submitted to Science of the Total Environment (under review)
 - Distance to roads, lower population density and road density influence strongly how much silence is “heard” → conference paper by Barros et al. (Forum Acusticum 2025)
 - Geospatial features obtained mainly by OpenStreetMap (related to weather, anthropogenic activity, traffic and green infrastructure) could explain 15% of the variance in daytime pleasantness → journal paper by Barros et al. → to be submitted to Environmental Research (May 2025)

Large Sound Survey - demographics

N = 9939 participants

Mean age 51.7 years old (SD=14.4)

78.1% is higher educated

Participants by City

Participants by Province

Participant Gender

Participants by Dwelling Type

Large Sound Survey – traffic noise annoyance

Remark: self-selection bias → more annoyed people participated in this survey

Noise annoyance by cars (Ghent)

- Not at all: 13.1%
- Slightly: 32.1%
- Moderately: 26.4%
- Strongly: 20.6%
- Extremely: 7.8%

Noise annoyance by planes (Leuven)

- Not at all: 53.1%
- Slightly: 27.7%
- Moderately: 11.6%
- Strongly: 5.8%
- Extremely: 1.8%

Noise annoyance by trams/metro (Antwerp)

- Not at all: 74.8%
- Slightly: 13.7%
- Moderately: 6.6%
- Strongly: 3.4%
- Extremely: 1.4%

Results? Large Sound Survey – noise annoyance

79.4% of participants

reported they are moderately to extremely annoyed by environmental noise (M=3.18, SD=.89)

Participants...

- who were relatively noise sensitive
- living in an apartment or studio
- who were adults
- living in cities with higher population densities

...reported more noise annoyance

Road traffic, construction, air traffic, (un)loading of cargo, music, people, and various neighborhood noise are prominent sources of noise annoyance - for participants who are moderately to extremely annoyed

Teaser 3: Smart sound sensor network

Antwerp

Ghent

Leuven

Smart sound sensor network

1475 citizen locations (6 weeks) + 73 fixed locations (1 year) + 20 locations near noise barrier (6 months)

Wide variety of acoustical indicators and third-octave spectra saved per second
 → averages per 15 minutes / hour / day / measurement period

MEL spectra (48 bands from 40-16000 Hz, 32 spectra per second) saved for further sound source recognition
 (e.g. current label = road traffic → future label = car/truck/bus/motorcycle/...)

Planned analyses:

- Explanation of “outliers”: weather conditions or events (music/sport/...)
- Correlation with Large Sound Survey & weekly surveys (annoyance and sleep quality)
- Correlation with strategic noise maps (L_{den} and L_{night})
- Correlation between outdoor and indoor L_{night} and sleep quality (100 locations)
- ...

L_{den}
 L_{day}
 $L_{evening}$
 L_{night}
 L_{Aeq} & L_{Ceq}
 $L_{Ceq} - L_{Aeq}$
 $L_{Aeq, moving\ av.}$
 $L_{Ceq, moving\ av.}$
 L_{Amax} & L_{Cmax}
 L_{Amin} & L_{Cmin}
 $L_{A0.5} \dots L_{A99.5}$
 $L_{C0.5} \dots L_{C99.5}$
 $L_{A10} - L_{A90}$
 $L_{C10} - L_{C90}$
 Harmonica index
 Int. Ratio
 σ_{AS} & σ_{CS}
 $ENL_{Aeq, 15. min.} + 10$
 $EN55 \dots EN85$

Smart sound sensor network in Antwerp

Conclusions

Challenging and multidisciplinary citizen science project (the largest in ...?)

Long lead time needed (since May 2022): partners/budget, elaborate scientific program, communication plan, public procurement, ethics committee approvals, logistics, DPIA, DMP, ...

Finding sufficient participants more difficult than expected

Participants in De Oorzaak significantly more annoyed than participants in governmental surveys (self-selection bias)

Still unclear how performant the AI models will be in the urban environment (training last AI model as we speak) → further developments needed/interesting

Gigantic amount of data, both subjective and objective → follow-up projects needed

Possible spin-offs: The Netherlands, Brussels (Belgium), Firenze (Italy), ... (discussions ongoing / EU Horizon Zero-pollution cities proposal submitted)

Collaboration (sensors/data)? → contact me: cedric.vuye@uantwerpen.be

**Thank you for your
attention!**

**Are there any
questions?**

**Thank you to all involved colleagues: Jonas
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**Thank you to all partners!
Thank you to all citizen scientists!**